

Synthetic and Solid State Structural Studies of Iron(II) and Iron(III) Complexes incorporating 1,3-Bis(aceto)benzimidazolin-2-thione and Heterocyclic Amines

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1,3-Bis(aceto)benzimidazolin-2-thione (L^1) was condensed with 2-amino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L^2), 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L^3), 2-amino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (L^4) and 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (L^5) followed by addition of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} salts. The solid complexes thus isolated were characterised by elemental analysis, spectral (ir, electronic, esr and Mössbauer) data, in addition to room temperature and variable temperature for $[FeL_{1/2}L^3Cl_2OH]$ and $[FeL_{1/2}L^5Cl_2OH]$ only magnetic moment. Cyclic voltammogram of the complex $[FeL_{1/2}L^5Cl_2OH]$ was also studied.

Owing to the greater significance of dinuclear/polynuclear Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} complexes as a model of metalloenzymes, a good account of the work has been reported in the literature recently¹⁻³.

In continuation to our earlier interest on the synthesis of Schiff bases⁴ derived from heterocyclic amines and heterocyclic aldehydes and as a search for new dinucleating ligands, we found it worthwhile

lowered to 1 502–1 456 cm^{-1} . This indicates the coordination of NH_2 group of L^5 with the metal ions.

The free ligand (L^1) peak observed at 1 718 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=O}$ is shifted to 1 633 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes which indicates its participation in coordination with the metal ion. However, this could be either due to the formation

Fig. 1.

to condense 1,3-bis(aceto)benzimidazolin-2-thione having diketo groups with biologically significant heterocyclic amines (L^2 – L^5 , Fig. 1). In addition to the above significance, the recent report on the triazole complexes of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} showing spin crossover phenomena⁵⁻⁷ also enthused us to carry out variable temperature magnetic moment studies of some of the triazole and thiadiazole complexes.

Results and Discussion

The empirical composition of the complexes based on the analytical data is shown in Table 1. Ir spectra of the triazole (L^5) complexes showed ν_{NH_2} at 3 325 cm^{-1} which is lowered as compared to the free ligand (L^5) peak at 3 454 cm^{-1} , and δ_{NH_2} of the free ligand (L^5) observed at 1 533 cm^{-1} is also

of Schiff base $\nu_{C=N}$ or due to coordinated $\nu_{C=O}$. But the appearance of peak due to coordinated ν_{NH_2} discards the possibility of the formation of Schiff base and is also consistent with the earlier report⁸. Thus the peak observed at ~1 633 cm^{-1} in the complexes is assigned to coordinated $\nu_{C=O}$.

The bands observed at 1 425–1 500 cm^{-1} due to (NH–CS–) in the spectra of the free ligand L^5 remains almost constant in the spectra of the complexes showing its non-participation in the coordination with the metal ion. Similar coordination modes were also observed in the spectra of the complexes derived from L^2 , L^3 and L^4 ligands.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} nm
		S	Cl	M		
1.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^2\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	19.12 (20.31)	17.80 16.02	13.52 14.17)	5.20	270, 340, 490, 640, 660
2.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^3\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	9.60 (10.96)	15.19 16.21	12.22 12.75)	5.80	260, 275, 485, 640, 660
3.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^4\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	3.29 (3.65)	15.15 16.21	13.62 14.17)	4.75	305, 370, 490, 640, 730
4.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	10.41 (10.59)	14.80 15.67	11.76 11.76)	6.25	220, 270, 300, 395, 460, 490, 640, 670
5.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^2\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	26.27 (25.63)	— —	12.80 12.78)	5.43	310, 760, 480, 650
6.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^3\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16.42 (16.63)	— —	11.38 11.61)	4.74	225, 280, 370, 485, 640
7.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^4\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	9.50 (9.89)	— —	12.96 11.61)	5.83	280, 295, 360, 440, 650, 665
8*.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^5\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15.62 (16.13)	— —	11.74 11.26)	5.20	270, 315, 370, 475, 570, 650

*Although containing mixed oxidation state, yet change of one proton has insignificant change in the calculated values. Compositions represented are same as for others in view of structural similarity.

TABLE 2—ESR AND MOSSBAUER SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF SOME OF THE IRON COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Is^* ΔEQ		Is^{**} ΔEQ		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}
		(mm s ⁻¹)		(mm s ⁻¹)			
1.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^4\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	0.34	0.68	—	—	2.45	2.45
2.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$	0.34	0.68	—	—	2.45	2.40
3.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^2\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	0.34	0.66	—	—	—	—
4.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^4\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	0.38	1.25	0.99	2.88	—	—
5.	$[\text{FeL}_{1/2}^1\text{L}^5\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	0.30	0.64	0.97	2.33	—	—

*For Fe^{III} complexes. **For Fe^{II} complexes partially oxidised to Fe^{III}.

The spectra of the complexes derived from Fe^{II} salt showed additional broad band at 1 200–1 050 cm⁻¹ centered at 1 110–1 115 cm⁻¹ along with the weak band at 970–980 cm⁻¹ due to bridging bidentate SO₄²⁻ group⁹. The broadness of the peak in this region could be due to overlapping by $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ of (L¹) which is expected to be present in the same region¹⁰. The presence of terminal OH group in the Fe^{III} complexes is assigned by the peak observed at 3 410 cm⁻¹ in their spectra. However, in the spectra of the complexes derived from Fe^{II} salt, the terminal

OH group may be distinguished from the aquo group by the peak due to $\delta_{\text{M}-\text{OH}}$ observed at 1 190 cm⁻¹.

Since far-ir region of the spectra of all the complexes was found to be overlapped with the free ligand peaks, therefore $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$ (terminal and bridging both) could not be distinguished.

In the electronic spectra of the complexes, bands observed at 360–280 nm (Table 1) could be assigned to (L→M) charge transfer bands as Fe is

observed to be in Fe^{III} state. In addition to this, the solid state spectra of these complexes showed a weak peak at 490–660 nm which could be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition, while the peaks observed at still higher energies could be due to intra-ligand transition¹¹.

Esr spectral data of some of these complexes at room temperature are reported in Table 2 while the spectral pattern of one complex $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^2\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ is shown in Fig. 2. The magnetic moment of the complexes at room temperature is shown in Table 1 which lies in the normal range of Fe^{III} high-spin complexes¹². However, the magnetic moments of $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^3\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ and $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ at -50 , -100 and -150° gave almost constant values as 1.09, 1.10, 1.07 and 0.89, 0.91 and 0.89 B.M. respectively, which on a preliminary level show the change of spin state (from high-spin to low-spin state). However, this calls for a deeper study using variable temperature Mössbauer spectra, but lack of instrumental facilities restricted the further studies.

Fig. 2. Powder esr spectra of $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^2\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ at room temperature.

The room temperature ${}^{57}\text{Fe}$ Mössbauer spectra of the complex $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ (Fig. 3a) show single doublet peak characterised by the quadrupole splitting and isomer shift (Table 2). The high-spin pseudo-octahedral geometry around Fe^{III} could be assigned on the basis of the earlier report¹³. The complexes derived from Fe^{II} salt also show similar spectrum. Fig. 3b as shown by the Fe^{III} complexes which indicates the complete conversion of Fe^{II} \rightarrow Fe^{III} in the complexes due to aerial oxidation.

The complex $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ shows mixed oxidation state containing Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} (Fig. 3c) and the measured ratio¹⁴ of Fe^{II}/Fe^{III} in this complex was found to be 62.5/37.5(%).

Fig. 3. Mössbauer spectra at room temperature of (a) $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$, (b) $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^3\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and (c) $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{SO}_4\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

The cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ in DMF (Fig. 4) shows two peaks at -1.2 and 0.70 V which could be due to the reduction of Fe^{III} \rightarrow Fe^{II} and back. It indicates the almost reversible nature of the process.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram (100 mV s^{-1}) of $[\text{FeL}_{1/2}\text{L}^5\text{Cl}_2\text{OH}]$ in DMF.

Thus on the basis of the empirical composition, spectral studies and physical properties like

insolubility and high thermal stability¹⁵ of the complexes, the following tentative polymeric structure could be assigned to all complexes as shown as Fig. 5.

For Fe^{III} complexes, Y = Cl, Z = OH, W = Cl
 For Fe^{II} complexes, Y = SO₄, Z = OH, W = H₂O
 Fig. 5.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary using an electrothermal Gallencamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Chlorine, sulphur and iron were determined by reported methods¹⁶. Electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carry14 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Jasco FT-IR-5300 spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-109 spectrometer at I.I.T., Kanpur. Magnetic moments at room temperature were obtained on a Cahn Farady electrobalance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as callibrant, and making diamagnetic corrections¹⁷. Variable temperature magnetic measurements were made at University Sophisticated Instruments Centre, Roorkee University, Roorkee, on a PAR vibrating sample magnetometer-155. Mössbauer spectra were recorded at Kyushu University, Japan, and the details of the experimental techniques are reported elsewhere¹⁸. Cyclic voltammogram was obtained at I.I.T., Kanpur, using biopotentiostat model RDE-4-pine instrument connected to an x-y recorder (model 2000, Houston Instrument) and NaClO₄(10⁻² M) was used as supporting electrolyte.

Metal salts and solvents were of reagents grade and the reactions were carried out in open atmosphere. 1,3-Bis(aceto)benzimidazolin-2-thione (L¹) was prepared and characterised by the method reported in the literature¹⁹. Other ligands (L²-L⁵) were also synthesised and characterised by the literature procedures²⁰⁻²³.

The complexes were prepared by slow addition of FeCl₃ solution (2 mmol, 324 mg in 10 ml of ethanol) to an ethanolic solution of L¹ (1 mmol, 234 mg in 10 ml of ethanol) followed by dropwise addition of L²-L⁵ (2 mmol each in 5 ml of ethanol) respectively, with constant stirring. The respective reaction mixtures were then made alkaline (pH 8-9) by the addition of saturated aqueous sodium carbonate solution, which immediately gave dark brown precipitates. Stirring was further continued for 0.5 h and the solid products were washed with water to remove the excess amount of sodium carbonate followed by hot ethanol and then dried at ~50°. The complexes with Fe^{II} salt were also prepared similarly using FeSO₄.7H₂O as metal salt.

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